

*In an increasingly AI-driven world, how is our ability
to think for ourselves changing?*

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July 2025

Introduction

Human ability to think for themselves is defined as *to make your own decisions and form your own opinions, without depending on other people* (“Think for yourself”). In a broader sense, it could be replaced by: *forming opinions independently of pressure and influence*. Today’s world – dominated by Artificial Intelligence (AI) – is centered on increasing speed and the amount of work done, rather than on its value. While the rapid advancement of AI has facilitated life in many areas, it also raised concerns about the state of independent thinking.

There is no doubt that AI – even unconsciously – impacts our thinking process, subtly shaping our way of processing, analysing and interpreting information. However, it is only a tool that can yield either positive or negative effects, depending on its utilization. This essay will explore how AI influences our cognitive processes and impacts our capacity to think for ourselves.

Exploration and argumentation

Continuous presence of AI in everyday tasks – voice assistants, predictive texts, autocorrect – and its unconscious actions – e.g. selection of viewed news, ads and information, raises concerns about the development of independent thinking, memory and problem-solving. Mentioned activities narrow people's worldview and reduce capacity for critical reflection, promoting intellectual laziness – *ipso facto* passive consumption of information with lack of desire to engage or challenge new material. Pariser (2011) argues that so-called *personalized* suggestions trap individuals in a *filter* bubble - the same range of beliefs, reinforcing existing beliefs and fostering homogeneity of thinking.

Another genre of everyday AI tools are the reminders or helpers – navigation, calendars, schedulers – designed to optimize efficacy and convenience, unfortunately creating a world where independent opinion becomes rather optional than an essential function. Additionally, they diminish our memory and recall of events, as we do not have a need to actively remember facts. One of the existing phenomena, referred to as the Googleas the Google *effect*, is a decrease in evoking facts and distinguishing between relevant and irrelevant information – between knowledge and the thought process necessary to interpret it; occurring as a result of outsourcing memory or analysis tasks to AI systems (Sparrow et al.). Unused neural pathways in the brain weaken or "fade" over time (Pauscal-Leone et al.). Following this line of reasoning, when we stop using critical thinking neuron pathways in our brain – what will happen?

Nowadays, AI is widely and commonly used in education, whether in schools or homes. AI-powered tools, like automated tutoring systems or personalized learning platforms, offer the possibility of enhancing independent learning, due to individualized support and feedback. It facilitates works by accessing relevant literature, checking grammar, or citation style. Real-time feedback can help users adjust their thinking process or take into account alternative solutions. One of the main arguments highlighting the positive impact of AI is its ability to augment critical and innovative thinking – through offering multiple perspectives and advices, or providing contrary data, e.g., ChatGPT models or Sematic Scholar (Yavich).

AI has proven to be particularly useful in work settings, such as medicine, where systems like surgeon robots or diagnostic programmes support doctors, even outperforming them in certain tasks. Its systems are designed to process and analyse vast amounts of data in a short time, producing concrete and accurate results. Furthermore, AI can help individuals understand complex problems by looking at them from different angles, with a wider range of data, enhancing decision-making capacity and cognitive development (Topol).

Nonetheless, it is important to remember that AI are just algorithms, which can make mistakes and expose gendered, racial, or socio-economic biases in the way of proposing or describing answers. For example, AI can prioritize mainstream narratives rather than marginalized perspectives and undermine cognitive diversity (Noble). Described errors can often be forgotten or overshadowed by faith in the infallibility or omnipotence of technology. Availability and speed of AI tools makes it easier to rely on them alone, not checking or considering different points of view – *de facto* fostering dependent thinking.

Lastly, the final defect of AI systems thinking process is one of its strengths – complete reliance on data and facts. It is worth remembering that humans are different from machines due to empathy - the ability to feel emotions and take them into account when analysing a situation. Our thinking processes are always irreversibly impacted by our feelings, hormones and body signals – conditions that machines lack. Unfortunately, as we entrust more decisions to be made by AI, without undermining them, this process erodes, diminishing our empathy, creativity and thinking skills.

As AI takes over human decision-making, it reshapes the very nature of human cognition, leading us to a question: *how much of our own thinking and decisions is still our own?* Carr (2014) while stating this question argues that the encroachment of AI into personal and professional domains may reshape the foundations of human cognition, leading us to outsourcing decision-making and thinking processes to technology, cultivating lethargy.

Conclusion

AI must be designed as an enabler, rather than a substitute -substitute -substitute - emphasizes scientists, setting an example of proper AI use (Jose et al.). While AI undoubtedly creates a potential of facilitating and improving life in terms of efficacy and convenience, it poses significant challenges to independent thinking and human autonomy. Through its ever-present influence in daily life, it may unconsciously lead to passive consumption, dependence and intellectual laziness. In spite of this, if used with caution and thoughtfulness - as an aid to decision-making - it can still facilitate innovation and a worldview, fulfilling its primary purpose.

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